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The Tourism Development Strategies of Hinako Islands in West Nias in Increasing the Regional Original Revenue and the Local People's Welfare

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Abstract

West Nias Regency has an enormous potential tourist destination, namely the Hinako Islands which consists of eight beautiful small islands. Yet the limited infrastructure and capacity of human resources have become the obstacle for this potential. The purpose of this study is to provide recommendations for tourism development strategies in the Hinako Islands to increase local government revenues (PAD) and the welfare of local communities. The research question is how is the strategy of the local government in developing tourism in the Hinako Islands?. This research is a field research, qualitative analytical descriptive type. The primary data of the research were observation and in-depth interviews, also supported by secondary data in the form of documentation and relevant literature studies. This study recommends a tourism development model consisting of 3 elements, namely: 1) West Nias Regency Government as a facilitator to provide tourism facilities and infrastructure; And as a regulator to formulate and enforce tourism business rules for the benefit of the Regional Original Income (PAD) and bring prosperity to local communities. 2) Private, namely existing investors, new investors with an ecotourism pattern, and village-owned enterprises (BUM-Des) to work on the industry in the concept of tourism agromina. 3) Community, to be a friendly host for tourists by providing guarantees for tourist safety, maintaining environmental cleanliness, and providing memorable experiences for tourists. The recommended strategies include strategies for developing tourism destinations, the tourism industry, tourism marketing, and tourism institutions.

Keywords: Ecotourism, Tourism Agromina, Regional Tourism Development Model

1. Introduction

1.1 Research Background

Indonesia is the largest archipelagic country in the world. One-third of Indonesia's territory is land and the other two-thirds is sea. Indonesia's mainland includes five large islands and around 17,000 small islands. The location of Indonesia's territory is at the equator and so the sun shines on these islands all year round. Therefore, Indonesia's nature is beautiful and rich in biodiversity. It is definitely tourism potential in Indonesia. The central government of Indonesia continues to boost the tourism sector. For the two consecutive years before the COVID-19 pandemic, the tourism sector was the country's largest foreign exchange earner in the periode of 2018 and 2019 totaling USD

19.2 billion and USD 20 billion respectively (Anton Setiawan, 2021). However, there was a decline of around 80% during the pandemic.

One of the most beautiful islands is the Hinako Islands. The islands consist of 8 small islands. These islands are administratively under Sirombu Sub District, West Nias District. The islands are one of the outermost parts of the western side of Indonesia and these border to the Indian Ocean. Of these 8 islands, 5 islands, namely Hinako Island, Bogi Island, Bawa Island, Asu Island, and Imana Island are in inhabited condition. While the other three islands from Heruanga Island, Hamutala Island to Langu Island are uninhabited islands. Nevertheless, the nature in the Hinako Islands is very beautiful and still awake.

Asu Island is in the northernmost of the Hinako Islands. The name of the ASU island is taken from the Nias language *Aurifa Safuriata Urugi*, which means the last life. It is called like that among the Hinako Islands, the Asu Island was the last island discovered by the ancestors of the Nias tribe. Many world-class surfers from various countries are settling from May to October in the Asu Island. They go surfing every day, befriend sharks and play in the waves. They also go on marine tours and enjoy fresh fish, lobster and various seafood. The Asu Island was developed by an American citizen in collaboration with a tourism businessman from Bali who has an international marketing network.

On the other hand, West Nias District is listed in Presidential Regulation (*Perpres*) Number 63 / 2020 regarding Determination of Disadvantaged Regions for the period of 2020-2024. In the scope of North Sumatra Province, the West Nias District's Human Development Index is still at the bottom of the 33 cities districts (BPS Sumatera Utara, 2019). Data from the Population and Civil Registration Office of West Nias District show that total population of this district amounts to 96,443 people and 56,103 people are not in school. In the West Nias District's Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2019 regarding the Master Plan for Tourism Development of West Nias District, the Hinako Islands are a strategic area for Marine Ecotourism, and the tourism sector has not been recorded as contributing to the Regional Original Income (PAD).

Solutions to this condition need to be looked for because tourism has several objectives among others: Increasing economic growth; Improving people's welfare; Eradicating poverty; Overcoming unemployment; Preserving nature, environment, and resources (Undang-Undang Nomor 10 Tahun 2009 Tentang Kepariwisata, 2009).

1.2 Tourism, Ecotourism, Agrotourism, Agromina Tourism

Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 10 of 2009 regarding Tourism states that tourism is a variety of tourist activities with the support of various facilities and services that the community, businessmen, government and local governments have provided. The research (Tegar & Saut Gurning, 2018) records that marine and coastal tourism are the oldest form of tourism and the largest tourism segment in the world. It is recorded that 5000 yachts enter the territory of Indonesia every year. Tourism is currently the economic activity with the fastest growth rate. However, it is also accused of having an impact on the natural destruction and frequently it does not bring prosperity to the local people. From here the concept of ecotourism emerges and it gives priority to the natural sustainability and the local people's welfare. According to Gunawan & Ortis (2012) in (Mba, 2020) ecotourism is defined as a form of sustainable tourism that aims to distribute benefits more broadly among stakeholders and inhabitants. Moreover, the research (Koroy et al., 2017) and (Rohani & Purwoko, 2020) recommend that tourism in small islands should definitely adopt the concept of ecotourism than mass tourism because the tourism will have a strong impact on the physical, social, cultural and economic environment of the islands.

Furthermore, in this ecotourism context, the concept of agrotourism emerges. According to (Suryawan, I Wayan Dedi WindiaA, I Wayan Sarjana, 2018), agrotourism is defined as a form of tourism activity that utilizes agricultural business activities as a tourist attraction. Agriculture here includes five sub-sectors, i.e.: food crops, forestry, plantations, livestock and fisheries. The fisheries referred to in the agrotourism are inland fisheries. (Yudasmara, 2016) also explains the concept of *minawisata*, i.e. the integration of marine and fisheries-based community economy into tourism. The concept of mina tourism is not as popular as agrotourism. The Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries is an institution that has been popularizing the tourism considering that 2/3 of

Indonesia's territory is sea, and marine tourism is the largest tourism potential in the world. Therefore, agro-tourism can be understood as a form of tourism that integrates the activities of farming and fishing communities in the context of tourism.

1.3 Tourism, Regional Original Revenue, Public Development

Concerning the Regional Original Revenue fund (hereinafter referred to as PAD), (Madiana, 2021) states that the contribution of the tourism sector to PAD in Gianyar District for 15 years OR the period of 2002 - 2017 is 44.71% in average. This government revenue comes from Hotel Restaurant Tax (PHR) and retribution on tourist and sports places. A research on how an islands region should start cultivating its regional potential in the tourism industry to increase PAD was carried out by (Coster et al., 2017) in Anambas District, Riau Islands Province. Anambas District originally had a large PAD from the revenue sharing of oil and gas exploration in the waters of the Anambas Islands. However, when the exploration contract was completed in 2013, the PAD funds from this sector remained at 8% in 2014 and 4% in 2015. On the other hand, the Anambas District government has not prepared itself and it does not prepare the community in the tourism industry as an alternative PAD fund.

Many researches on tourism in favor of the community development have been carried out. (Wulandari et al., 2020) found that the community involvement was the key word in every step from initial planning, development to management. A research (Sero, 2015) in the beaches of Tagalaya, Kumo and Kakara, North Halmahera Islands, the majority of which have low education recommended the importance of learning community perceptions to be integrated into the tourism development. The Research (Mba, 2020) found that a role model was required from within the local people, i.e. those who are open to building networks with various parties. (Ciptosari et al., 2019) found that at the pilot stage, local entrepreneurship arises as a result of interaction with tourists, and bonding social capital has a major role. However, at a certain point the local people are unable to compete with foreign investors who are more professional, and the social bonding becomes a barrier for successful local entrepreneurs because the debt requests from relatives and neighbors are difficult to refuse. Finally, (Panjaitan & Siagian, 2019) emphasizes the importance of strategy as the art of combining key success factors.

Based on various existing researches, the researchers have developed a tourism development model as follows:

Figure 1: Regional Tourism Development Model

From field conditions and the various researches having been described at above, this research aims to provide recommendations for tourism development strategies in the Hinako Islands to increase the Regional Original Revenue (PAD) and the local people's welfare. While the formulation of the research problem is how the tourism development model of the Hinako Islands as a strategy to increase the Regional Original Revenue (PAD) and the local people's welfare. The recommended strategies include the tourism destination development strategies, the tourism industry, tourism marketing, and tourism institutions.

2. Research Methods

This research was conducted in the Hinako Islands under West Nias District administratively. The research was conducted for 5 months, i.e. from May to September 2021. This research uses a qualitative descriptive method because the researchers intend to describe the existing phenomena by analyzing and presenting facts systematically to facilitate the understanding and drawing conclusions. According to (John W Creswell and David J., 2018), qualitative research is an approach to explore and understand the meaning of individuals or groups in relation to social or human problems. The research process involves questions and procedures that appear, and the data is usually collected in a participant setting. Moreover, the data analysis is inductively constructed from specifics to general themes and finally the researchers makes interpretations of the meaning of the data. The final written report has a flexible structure. Those who engage in this form of research support a way of looking at a research that respects an inductive style, focus on individual meaning, and the importance of reporting on the complexity of situations.

The subject of this research is the tourism of the Hinako Islands and the object of this research is the development strategy of the Hinako Islands tourism development. This research uses two types of data sources, i.e. primary data and secondary data. The primary data sources come from interviews, Focus Group Discussions (FGD), and field observations, and the secondary data sources are literature studies, local government agencies (related agencies), and other relevant sources. The data collection techniques are carried out through field observations, interviews, FGDs, documentation, literature studies, monitoring mass media and social media. The validity of the data is through triangulation of three sources.

The data analysis technique in this research uses the SWOT analysis, i.e. the identification of internal and external factors systematically to formulate the strategies by maximizing Strengths, reducing Weaknesses, taking Opportunities and overcoming Threats.

3. Research Result and Discussion

As has been explained previously, (Wulandari et al., 2020) and (Sero, 2015) show that the involvement and perception of the local people about tourism will determine the success of developing a destination. In this matter, this research positions the community as a subject in the tourism development of the Hinako Islands. The development starts from "what are the local people's wishes/expectations." The activities to accommodate these aspirations can also be used as a means of socialization. The village head of Balowondrate, who also works as a speed boat driver, has conveyed what the local people's wishes and perceptions as follows:

I want tourism here because we can receive the boat rental service or other money right away. For copra, our trees are getting older and so the fruit is getting less and the trees are getting taller and so it is dangerous for coconut pickers. After becoming copra, the Sitoli people (researcher: copra buyers from Gunung Sitoli City) determine the price. If we do not give them, they do not send a ship and our copra rots. When we cut down and replant, we wait a long time for the tree to bear fruit, and we have no income.

A housewife from the Hinako Islands who met the researchers said:

Where are you from, Ma'am? When will you come here again? We're waiting... come here again Ma'am... rarely people visit us.

Other data we get about Imana Island is that its inhabitants have abandoned the island and now they live in the Nias Island which the local people calls "Nias Darat" for the difficulty of livelihoods, transportation and communication. From these data, this study concludes that the people of the Hinako Islands have expectations to tourism and so it is relatively easy to be involved in the tourism development.

From the identification of internal and external factors and the SWOT analysis that we have carried out, this research formulates 10 Hinako Islands tourism development strategies. The government and related agencies at the central, provincial and regional levels, private sector, and local communities must carry them out.

Four strategies relate to tourist destinations, particularly the 3A elements of Accessibility (Accessibility, Amenity, Attraction) in tourism, i.e.:

1. Make other islands as tourist destinations as well because there is one of the eight islands that have been operating in tourism activities. It has been described previously that people have positive perceptions and expectations to tourism.
2. Provide tourism facilities and infrastructure in the Hinako Islands, in a kind of docking ports, street lighting, clean water installations, sewage treatment, internet network availability, and land and sea transportation. From the field observations, the journey from Binaka Airport to Sirombu seaport must be taken by road for about 3-4 hours because the road is winding, and there are many damaged roads and emergency bridges. The Sirombu port is in an unsuitable condition for tourism, and the docking port is only on the island of Asu built by the private sector, i.e. Puri Asu. The Internet signal is hard to come by along roads, ports and islands. There are no tariff arrangements for tourists for land and sea transportation to the Hinako Islands as well. Clean water treatment for the Hinaki Islands can be pursued on Bawa Island, which has 2 freshwater lakes that have been discussed as the tourist attractions.
3. Develop a disaster anticipation system related to the position of these small islands in the Indian Ocean and Law No. 10 of 2009 regarding Tourism mandates that the safety of tourists is a factor that must be guaranteed.
4. The regional development seeks funds from the central government or the private sector and it may not directly relate to tourism interests. However, the current development will still have a positive effect on tourism in this region.

Three strategies having been formulated relates to the tourism industry, i.e.:

1. It is consistent with (Peraturan Daerah Kabupaten Nias Barat Nomor 6 Tahun 2019 Tentang Rencana Induk Pembangunan Kepariwisata Nias Barat Tahun 2019-2025, n.d.) which stipulates that the Hinako Islands are a Strategic Marine Ecotourism Area.
2. When promoting the concept of agromina tourism as one of the missions of the West Nias District government for the period of 2021-2025, it integrates the daily lives of the local people of the Hinako Islands whose livelihood is from farmers of coconut plantations and fishermen into the tourism industry. The research (Sumantra et al., 2020) in the Subak Lepud area of Baha Village, Mengwi Sub-District, Bali highlights on how to provide a "feeling" of tourism in the local people's daily lives. Examples of the daily life of the Hinako Islands community that can be integrated into tourism include:

The coconut plantations of the local inhabitants can be changed to an outdoor restaurants. Green coconut and local fruits can be served as a tourist menu so as to increase their selling value. The traditional boats of the local inhabitants can be rented out for fishing or boating on the outskirts of the island. Bicycles owned by children in the Hinako Islands can be rented out for tourists to bike around the island. The local inhabitants of the Hinako Island who work as lobster seekers and reservoirs, can become tour guides in the activities and "story tellers" about lobster or do lobster cultivation which is used as a marine tourism attraction. In terms of entrepreneurship, the research (Ciptosari et al., 2019) show that the growth process of the community entrepreneurship results in the interactions with tourists.

What needs to be anticipated is the social jealousy. It occurs when certain local people achieve economic success, and the old conflict occurred between the local government of the previous period and the Sirombut coastal community regarding land ownership. The tourism development and economic progress that occurs in the Hinako Islands have the potential to cause social jealousy for the Sirombu coastal community who has a hard character. In fact the access to the Hinako Islands is the Sirombu port. The research (Mba, 2020) recommends that solving this problem is through dividing the segments in the tourism industry. This is also an opportunity for the West Nias District government to direct the Sirombu coastal community because they have great potential tourism, but they refuse to develop tourism in their area.

Table 1: Simulation of Involving Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) In Tourism Industry

No	Name of Islands	Name of Villages	Tourism Business
1	Hinako		
		1. Halamona	Homestay Cooking traditional food Handicrafts
		2. Hanofa	Restaurants, mini market
		3. Lahawa	Traditional boat rental services
		4. Hinako	Bicycle and sports equipment rental services
		5. Sinene'eto	Fish / lobster cultivation
		6. Balowondrate	Speed boat rental services
2	Bawa		
		1. Tuwa-tuwa	Drinking water processing
		2. Kao-kafo	Home Stay, restaurants
		3. Bawasawa	Sports equipment
3	Bogi		
		1. PulauBogi	Rented traditional boat
4	Imana		
		1. Bawosalo'o	Lobster / fish cultivation
		2. Imana	Restaurants
5	Asu		Home Stay, water sports equipment rental services
6	Heruanga		
7	Hamutala		
8	Langu		

Balowondrate village has 2 hamlets (*dusun*). One hamlet is in the Hinako Islands and the other is in *Pulau Nias* (Nias Island) which the local community calls “Nias Darat” (*Nias Mainland*). The village head who also works as a speed boat driver and is known as the “handler” of the storm, has a good social network and has ever worked for a company in Medan City. The village head frequently goes back and forth between “Nias Pulau” and “Nias Darat” and the local people of Sirombu port call him “Pak Kades.” The research (Gangsar Hanajayani dan Sariffuddin, 2018) notes the importance of the role of figures from within the local community in the development of tourist destinations and so, the local people have the perception that the government realizes the wishes of their community and otherwise, it does not instruct the local people to develop the tourist destinations.

Several alternatives for developing community-based ecotourism can be seen in a research of (Wisudawati, 2017) on the voluntourism program, which comes from the words *volunteer* and tourism in the village of Ubud, Bali; (Rohani & Purwoko, 2020) about the conservation and education tourism located in Pampang Village, Paliyan Sub-District, Gunung Kidul District, Special Region of Yogyakarta.

3. Enforcing the regulations related to the Regional Original Revenue (PAD) to industrial players

Enforcing the laws and regulations in the sector of the tourism industry is also an important point for the Regional Original Revenue of West Nias District. In addition to the Hotel Restaurant Tax (PHR) and retribution, the West Nias District government needs to regulate and enforce land, sea transportation rates, home stay prices and food prices. Therefore, tourists have the estimated travel costs to this region.

One marketing strategy having been formulated is as follows:

In addition to developing surfing tourism and the domestic market, the West Nias District government has to develop foreign tourists who are in the market niche. Data from (Tegar & Saut Gurning, 2018) show that that marine and coastal tourism is the oldest form of tourism and the largest tourism segment in the world.

The observations to Asu Island show that up to now the tourism products have only focused on surfing sports during the wave season from May to October. In this matter, marine sports such as diving, snorkeling, fishing, canoeing, cruising have not been developed seriously. By developing a niche market other than surfing, foreign tourists can also be brought in when the waves are calm from November to April. Therefore, the Hinako Islands tourism industry can produce throughout the year. For the purpose of boosting this Regional Original Revenue, large and professional investors are needed.

One institutional strategy is formulated in a kind of establishing a Tourism Business Association with the management structure on the basis of the existing social institutions in the local community by involving the government (tourism department and other related agencies) and the head of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUM Des) managing the tourism industry in the Hinako Islands.

This association can provide various benefits among others as follows:

1. Conveying messages of development, management and maintenance of tourist destinations and human resources in the tourism industry.
2. Monitoring the fund uses of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUM Des).
3. Coordination or cooperation between Village-Owned Enterprises (BUM Des) in the tourism development movement.
4. Sharing information between members in creating innovations and solving problems that occur in the field.

4. Conclusion

The potential of the Hinako Islands for marine ecotourism is definitely great. Barriers to the development of this potential relate to local human resources and infrastructure facilities. If properly managed, eco-tourism of the Hinako Islands will be able to provide the Regional Original Revenue for West Nias District in the great number and the local people's welfare. The recommended tourism development model for the Hinako Islands is the cooperation of three parties, i.e. : the government, the private sector and the community. The government will act as a facilitator in preparing tourism facilities and infrastructure and a regulator in relation to the input of the Regional Original Revenue and the regularity of tourism service tariffs. The private sector consisting of old investors, new investors and Village-Owned Enterprise (BUM Des) will work on the foreign tourist market in addition to surfers and domestic tourists by integrating their daily lives as coconut plantation workers and fishermen in the tourism industry with the concept of agromina tourism. The community plays a role in maintaining the security and cleanliness of the islands as well as providing a memorable experience for tourists.

Considering Indonesia's position on the equator line and its tourism potential in around 17,000 small islands, the development of people in these small islands is left behind if compared to those who live in five large islands. Therefore, research and development of agromina tourism needs to be carried out in various other locations.

5. Recommendations

This reserach recommends three novelties, i.e. the Regional Tourism Development Model; the concept of agromina tourism for destination of the Hinako Islands and other small islands; and developing the Village Owned Enterprises (BUM Des) to encourage emerging entrepreneurship in the local people particularly in the tourism industry.

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